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CHILDHOOD DISINTEGRATIVE DISORDER (CDD) EDUCATION A CASE STUDY AT NATURE SCHOOL OF BATURRADEN

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ABSTRACT

Observation aims to find out the behaviors of children with autism, the types of autism of children, the intervention program provided by Nature School of Baturraden. The research by a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data collection was done by observation, interviews and study documents. Data analysis was carried out qualitatively. There are 6 characteristics of autistic child development namely: Delay in language development, inability to interact with others, repetitive movements, behavioral problems, impaired sensory movement disorders, Different intellectual function from other children. Based on these characteristics students are encouraged by autism disintegration (Childhood Disintegrative Disorder). Through the process of several months, TK Alam (Nature Kindergarten School) Baturaden has an ICGT ((Integrated and comprehensive Green Therapy) program. This therapy has 6 special needs programs of Green Therapy for childhood education 1. Gifts given by Allah, God Almighty, 2. Motor sensory therapy, 3. Communication therapy, 4. Self-help Therapy, 5. Socialization therapy, 6. Academic and non-academic therapy. Behavior shown by children has begun to erode and can bring up unseen talents. As evidenced from observation, interviews and documentation, these students experienced positive satisfying changes, such as students' memorizing the Qur'an well in accordance with correct recitation

KEYWORDS: Autism Inclusive Education, Nature School of Baturraden, Assessment and Intervention.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of Sekolah Alam (Nature School) is the concept of education refers to the fulfillment of two functions of people in the world, namely humans as *Abdullah* or servants of Allah and humans as caliphs or leaders on earth (Damayanti et al., 2024). Humans as *Abdullah* or servants of Allah have the task of worshipping to Allah the Creator who has created nature and its contents. As *Abdullah*, humans have the obligation to obey and comply with Allah SWT. Teaching autistic children is not only possible, but also important. A person with autism can have different forms when it comes to brain disorders. Some are severe in various light conditions. Children with autism need more help than mild autism who may have more freedom (Ekawati & Pujiati, 2023).

Children with autism having learning disabilities and other symptoms can take a lot of their teacher's attention and also disrupt class (Saliba & Cuschieri, 2021). This should not be a bad situation but it can benefit everyone. It even shows signs of improvement. Do you know that an autistic child will need more time and one-on-one attention? This is what works best for them. Parents or a special teacher can teach your child. It is possible that an autistic child needs a classic class room or special class (Denham et al., 2012).

In recent years developmental psychologists have increasingly been referred by pediatricians to consult children aged 2-4 years with symptoms like the illustration above. Autism, is one of the developmental disorders that is increasing at this time, causing deep anxiety for parents (Pujiati & Yulianto, 2021). Children with Autism disorders classified as Childhood Disintegrative Disorder (CDD) show normal development during the first 2 years of developmental age, then suddenly they lose the abilities that have been achieved previously. This observation will lead to several autistic disorders carried out by the observer at TK Alam Baturaden Purwokerto (Trawick-Smith, 2023).

These observations aimed to generally find out (1) behaviors in children with autism, (2) types of autism in children, (3) intervention programs provided by schools. Specifically, the purposes of this study were to find out (1) General description of the school; (2) Policies / regulations on inclusive education used as the basis; (3) Students with special needs studying in inclusive schools (types and characteristics); (4) Human Resources conditions in schools (abilities, attitudes, perceptions) including teachers, principals, administrative

personnel, etc. ; (5) Specific curriculum and how curriculum modifications are carried out; (6) The learning process taking place in the classroom (methods, strategies, classroom arrangements; (7) Environmental support and learning facilities in the classroom and at school, accessibility, special learning equipment, (8) Implementation of the evaluation, (9) Condition of supporting and inhibiting factors, attitudes of parents, community, supervisors, official offices, whether there is a source space and resource center, (10) The process of selection / recruitment of learners with special needs (Hikita et al., 2023).

2. THEORITICAL REVIEW

Autism is defined as a developmental disorder that is neurological and complex / complex characterized by barriers to communication activities, interactions, behavior, emotions and sensory (Pujiati, 2015). Autism is a developmental disorder that causes disturbances and obstacles in communication and social skills (Syaodih et al., 2021). Autism symptoms appear in various levels, ranging from mild to severe levels. Most children with autism have speech problems, but they have relatively good motor skills in general (Wahyuningsih et al., 2020) "Autism is a developmental disability that significantly affects a student's verbal and non verbal communication, social interaction, and educational performance and it often manifests in children by the age of three" (Sen et al., 2020). Autism is a developmental disorder that significantly affects students' verbal and non verbal communication, social interaction, and academics often occur in children aged three years (Nu'man et al., 2022).

At first the term "autism" was taken from schizophrenia disorders, where Bleuler used this autism to describe the behavior of schizophrenic patients who withdraw from the outside world and create their own fantasy world (Chan et al., 2023). But there is a clear difference between the causes of autism in schizophrenics and those with infantile autism (Yohanna & Maya, 2019). In schizophrenia, autism is caused by an area of mental disorder with hallucinations and delusions lasting for at least 1 month, whereas developmental failures classified as Pervasive Disorders with autistic life that are not accompanied by hallucinations and delusions were found in children with infantile autism (Thornton, 2019).

The definitions according to experts above can be summarized that autism has a neurological and complex development that is characterized by

barriers to communication, behavior, interaction, emotions and sensory activities. Brain development also faces obstacles due to several factors causing slow brain work (Purba, Pujiati, et al., 2025). This autism disorder has several classifications with special characteristics in each autism type. Therefore, the facilitator does not only stand alone in detecting special children. Facilitators must have a TEAM either with psychologists, medicine or practitioners who are involved in the world of ABK (Children with Special Needs). So that it can enforce correctly and appropriately intervene in children.

2.1. Classification/ Type

Autism according to Dsm Iv is Pervasive Developmental Disorder (Pdd) developmental disorders that are spread, namely:

1. Autistic Disorder (Autism) is developmental disorders that appear before the age of 3 years as indicated by the presence of obstacles in social interaction, communication and the presence of stereotypical behavior in interests and activities (WONDAL et al., 2025).
2. Asperger's Syndrome is a barrier to the development of social interaction and with limited interests and activities. In general, it does not show language and speech delays with average to above average level of intelligence.
3. Rett's Syndrome is more common in girls and rarely occurs in boys. The sufferers experience a normal development but then they lost the ability they have. Their loss of functional ability of the hand is replaced by repeated hand movements in the age range of 1-4 years (Pözl-Stefanec & Geißler, 2022).
4. Childhood Disintegrative Disorder (CDD) sufferers show normal development during the first 2 years of developmental age, then suddenly they lose their abilities they have before.
5. Pervasive Developmental Disorder - Not Otherwise Specified (PDD-NOS), referring to the term atypical autism, a diagnosis of PDD-NOS applies if a child does not show all the criteria for a particular diagnosis (Autism, Asperger or Rett Syndrome).

2.2. Developmental Characteristics

There are 6 characteristic description of autistic child development: 1). Delay in language development, 2). Inability to interact with other

people, 3). Repetitive movements, 4). Behavioral problems, 5). Limited directional sensory movement disorders, 6). Different intellectual function from other children (Sukmawati et al., 2024).

2.2.1. Causing Factor

From some research conducted by experts, it was found hypotheses about the possible triggers of autism and are classified into six factors, namely:

1. Genetic Or Hereditary Factors

Genetic is a strong factor in autistic children. If a member of a family has a history of autism, then his/her subsequent offspring will have a great chance of suffering from autism. This is due to genetic disorders that affect the development, growth and formation of brain cells. Genetic conditions triggering autism can be due to the old age of the father or mother during her pregnancy. It is known that the old men's sperm tend to easily mutate and trigger autism. In addition, mothers with diabetes are also identified as triggers of autism in infants (Nugraha & Rahmawati, 2020).

2. Gynecology Or Pranatal Factors

The womb condition can also cause symptoms of autism. This is caused by a virus that attacks the first trimester, namely the rubella syndroma virus. It is also known that environmental health also affects the health of the fetus in the womb. Air pollution has a negative impact on fetal brain and physical development, thus it increases the likelihood of babies born with the risk of autism. It was even found that underweight babies born prematurely is also a risk of autism.

3. Birth Factors

Babies born with low weight, prematurely, or staying longer in the womb (more than 9 months) are at risk of developing autism (Indah & Rohmah, 2020). In addition, babies who experience respiratory failure (hypoksa) at birth are also at risk of experiencing autism (Nainggolan et al., 2018).

A. Environmental Factor

Normal and healthy babies can also happen to experience autism. External environmental factors, such as a stressful and unclean environment, can also cause babies to suffer from autism (Pujiati et al., 2020). Through the mother, unclean environment can cause the babies allergic. Therefore, mothers are supposed to avoid exposure to allergic sources such as cigarette smoke, dust, or foods that cause allergies (Zanobini & Solari, 2019).

B. Drug Factor

Drugs to treat nausea and vomiting or tranquilizer consumed by pregnant women are at risk of causing children with autism, therefore it is a must to consult with a doctor before taking any type of medication during pregnancy (Jawaldeh et al., 2020).

C. Food Factor

The chemicals contained in food are very dangerous for the womb. One of them is pesticide exposure to vegetables. It is known that pesticides disrupt the function of genes in the central nervous system, causing autistic children.

3. METHODS

This study uses a case study method to examine and obtain a general depiction of the development and education of Autistic Children. The qualitative approach was selected to express certain social situations by describing reality correctly. It is described by words based on data collection techniques and analysis of relevant data obtained from natural situations (Pearson et al., 2020). This study described the aspects with important values related to the research objectives in detail. This research was conducted in the Baturaden, Purwokerto.

The observations were conducted with the teacher / facilitator on the development and education of autistic children with disintegration at Early childhood Alam Baturaden (Fusaroli et al., 2023). The complete picture was done in accordance with the research objectives. Then, in-depth interviews was done to collect several data conducted to get the research objectives (Buzzelli, 2018). The interviews were conducted on regular students, especially students with special needs. These interviews were also conducted to find out opinions of the teacher of regular students towards students with special needs during teaching and learning activities in the classroom (Caspi et al., 2020). The use of instruments based on research objectives is the instrument. Interview activity was done freely. Interviews were carried out in a flowing manner during break time. Documentation techniques in this study are used to collect records of events (Tustin, 2021). Observations in this study were carried out by directly involving the researcher in the situation under study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Allah SWT, the Almighty God, has provided

nature and the environment as the best medium for children's learning. In fact, many schools fetter children with "monotonous in class" activities. Children accept the theory without being given much flexibility to find out the causal process (Azman et al., 2022). In fact, children are supposed to become strong learners. They are full of curiosity, always amazed by what is happening around them, fond of moving and asking (Manolitsi & Botting, 2011).

TK Alam Baturaden is a fresh oasis, especially for children with special learning styles, and children with differentiated curriculum needs. I see the application of active learning in SD SABar (this school) is able to apply the principle of "unconditional positive acceptance", through natural media and the surrounding environment, as well as the curriculum and all facilitators. SABar can improve the ability of the children whose competencies were previously invisible. The curriculum at SABar Green education is an environment-based curriculum. It educates children the importance of protecting the earth (Fadilah Utami et al., 2022).

Special children are God's gifts with their strengths and weaknesses. They were created with their own various talents (Fageeh et al., 2021). Therefore, the handling given must be special too. This school has a team that makes special programs for children according to the needs of each child. According to the educational figure KH. Dewantara "Education in general means the effort to advance children's personality (character, inner strength), mind and body in harmony with nature and society. In line with KH. Dewantara, the assessment was carried out through the play program in nature. The assessment implemented by this school is an assessment through play. It means that this activity puts play as a medium or means for assessing various achievements of child development (LeGrand et al., 2021).

Assessment is a systematic process of collecting data of a child. In the context of education, assessment serves to see the abilities and difficulties faced by someone at that time, as material to determine what is really needed. Based on that information, a teacher will be able to arrange realistic learning programs in accordance with the objective reality of the child. As an example; from the assessment results, when it obtained information that a child has difficulty in speaking, it did not mean that that child is Autistic. Furthermore, the assessment instrument was arranged to find very

specific things related to the problem of speech earlier without trying to find out global syndromes or labeling (Purba, Sagala, et al., 2025).

Educational programs are based on needs, and not on the record of a child. In the field assessment and evaluation, it often becomes cryptic and is used inappropriately. Evaluations and assessments do have similarities, but they are very different. Viewed from the implementation; The evaluation is carried out at the end of the learning process or when the learning process takes place in accordance with the conditions being evaluated (Brady et al., 2020), while the assessment action is not only done at the end and during learning process, but long before the learning process occurs, the assessment has been done and this process will continue to move endlessly. Judging from the content (instruments); the evaluation is taken from the material provided, while the assessment is based on the problems and abilities of the child. Evaluation is merely to measure how far the material can be absorbed or mastered, while the assessment is to see the condition of the child at that time in order to develop a learning program so that they can intervene appropriately (Melati et al., 2019).

Tests, diagnoses, evaluations and assessments are interrelated, but all four have different meanings. In conjunction with the development of individual learning programs (PPI), assessment becomes very central compared to tests, diagnostics and evaluations, because it is based on the results of the assessment that individual learning programs (PPI) can be arranged and developed. However, tests, diagnostics and evaluations are still important to know the whereabouts of children, but not for the benefit of programming. The main purpose of the assessment, in principle, is to determine how the current condition of an autistic child is. a modification of the assessment needs to be done to get a picture of the condition of an Autistic child at this time, so that the learning program arranged according to the circumstances and needs of each child (Oktavianingsih et al., 2021).

Developmental assessment is used to see the sequence and stages of child development that can help teachers understand the level and ability of children (Rofiki et al., 2022). The main purpose of Observation Technique is to see the children's abilities and skills in natural environmental situations. The behavior appears without any intervention and manipulation from the teacher. Data collected from observational activities may be closely related to humans (people), material or objects, and various situations related to students

(Bender et al., 2022).

According to Hapidi (Xiao et al., 2021), the use of a stimulating environment and facilitative techniques could provide relevant information for interventions. Some skills can be assessed with a play approach (Sajawandi et al., 2024).

This program still has the principle of a therapeutic program in general, however, children with special needs have more space in moving to gain experience, to receive insight, to hone skills, and to develop talent in one program that is integrated with nature as the main media.

There are 6 programs of SABar's interventions with children who have special needs with the ICGT (Integrated and comprehensive Green Therapy) including:

4.1. Image Of ICGT Therapy

1. Therapy for the gift given by Allah,
2. Motor sensory,
3. Communication,
4. Self-help, self-help efforts, namely self-care, self-help, and daily activities or Activities of Daily Living (ADL). In self-development, they are trained the skills needed to care for children daily, such as eating and drinking independently, self-cleaning (washing hands, washing feet, bathing, brushing teeth, defacting, urinating), combing hair, wearing clothing, etc.,
5. Socialization, exists with the needs of autism Disintegration requires a social environment that can accept them. Playing is one of the programs carried out so that children can socialize through role playing, group games etc.
6. Academic and non-academic therapy. Education carried out in an integrated manner with other children in this school. The unique is the handling of each child especially to a child with special needs. The facilitator tells other children in one class to understand the condition of children with special needs. ICGT therapy is done to every child who does not sleep. It is the best time to do this therapy and be done both at home and school. There are 3 special therapists for children who handle special children. When the special child is in the class, she is directly handled by the class teacher with the provisions on the knowledge of children with special needs (Ariyati & Fauzan, 2017). The parents' response about the results of the therapy treatment carried out by the TIM was extraordinary. The parents were happier to see their children in good developing condition because they were well treated in early childhood education Alam Baturraden.

One of the students, named Dn. He was the first grade of primary school. He was big like a robot. He used to experience tantrum, digestive disorders,

impaired perfective communication, and delays in talking. He always refused to eat rice. When the teacher realized this different special behavior from other friends, the teacher then tried to explore the causes of these problems (Fatkhurohman & Wartono, 2022). Through the help of the therapy team for almost 3 years, it can be seen the great development of Dn. He a child who became obedient, polite without any tantrums more. The ICGT program is tailored to the needs of students. One of amazing program done to Dn was memorizing the verses of the Koran. This memorization was not forced by Dn's parents. Dn was found so happy listening to the tape or video of the Qur'an. This became the habituation of Dn's life, for example when he was eating and drinking there must be any picture or symbol of AL quran

5. CONCLUSION

Autism is a disorder of childhood development

which is increasing in number today. But this does not mean that children who suffer from other developmental disorders such as slow speech, being very active and lack concentration are always considered to suffer from autism. Accuracy in diagnosing symptoms is needed because the overlapping of one disorder symptom with other symptoms happens very often. For this reason, an integrated examination from various experts is needed so that the diagnosis of the disorder is precisely enforced. The right diagnosis will produce the right prognosis and intervention.

For scientific purposes, autism disorders can be classified as mild-moderate and severe autism. However, this classification is rarely put forward to parents because it is expected to affect attitudes and interventions carried out. Yet for the handling and intervention between mild, moderate and severe autism is not very different. Handling and intervention must be intensive and integrated so as to provide optimal results.

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